

The Analysis of Web Scrapping Libraries of Python and Modulating a Price Intelligence using ScrappedData

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Abstract— A automated method for retrieving enormous amounts of information from websites is called web scraping. Much of this content is unstructured in HTML format and is turned into organized data using a database or spreadsheet so that it may be used in many applications. Web scraping can be carried out using a variety of approaches to gather data from websites. These include using specialized APIs, using web tools, or even building your own web scraping software from scratch. Python is the greatest language for web scraping, as can be seen from the way that web scrapers are created and developed using the various Python tools. The fact that Python is simple to learn, easy to understand, and easy to write in is one of the most crucial reasons to adopt Python for web scraping. Python provides a great selection of libraries, including Scrapy, BeautifulSoup, Selenium, and many others. These libraries are ideal for web scraping and additional processing of the collected data.

Keywords—web scraping, python scraping, scrapy, selenium, beautifulsoup, data mining

I. INTRODUCTION

Web scraping is a method for capturing data from the internet. Web harvesting as well as web data extraction are other names for it. Web scraping applications can directly access the World Wide Web through a web browser or the Hypertext Transfer Protocol. Web scraping can be done manually by a software user, but the term is frequently often used describe automated processes carried out by a robot or web-crawler. It is a sort of copying in which specific data is obtained and copied from the internet, typically into a centrally located storage or spreadsheet, for later retrieval or analysis..

A web page is retrieved and extracted from in order to scrape it. The downloading of a page is called fetching (which a browser does when a user views a page). In order to gather pages for later processing, The foundation of web scraping is web crawling.After being fetched, extraction can happen. The data on a page can be copied into a spreadsheet or imported into a database after it has been processed, searched, and reformatted. Web scrapers often steal something from a page so they can use it elsewhere for another reason.

II. PYTHON FOR WEB SCRAPPING

A. Diverse Libraries

A wide range of libraries are available for Python, including BeautifulSoup, Selenium, lxml, and many frameworks like Scrapy. These libraries are ideal for web scraping and additional processing of the collected data.

B. Ease To Use

Python is simple to code, to put it simply. Of fact, it is erroneous to think that someone without programming experience might quickly build a code for web scraping. However, it is more simpler to use than other languages because you do not need to include semicolons like ";" or curly brackets "" everywhere. This, according to many developers, is why Python is less disorganised. Python syntax is also simple to read and understand. To move between different code blocks, developers only need to use their mouse.

III. RELATED WORK

There are different libraries and packages included in python for web scraping which can be effectively used for scrapping huge amount of data from the web.

Prof. Usha Nandwani. et. al. [1] used the Selenium library in an attempt to extract the data and created it in csv file format. The script that was created to extract the data was very successful in easily locating each of these sources. Additionally, the study revealed the most popular material on the site chosen for testing in a percentage manner.

M. El Asikri et. al. [2] among various types of scraping, concentrate on methods that extract web page content. In the area of Web e-commerce, it adopts scraping techniques in particular. In order to achieve this, it suggests a technique that uses Python's scrapy framework to analyse data extraction via Web scraping.

Anjali Khute et. al. [3] introduces static and dynamic web scraping for effective data extraction and gives a fundamental understanding of data extraction, storage, and reuse. It can transform the unstructured data into an organised form with the aid of web scraping.


```
1 from selenium import webdriver
2 from selenium.webdriver.common.by import By
3 from selenium.webdriver.common.keys import Keys
4 PATH = "C:\Program Files\Google\Chrome\Application\chrome.exe"
5 driver = webdriver.Chrome(PATH)
6 driver.get("https://www.amazon.in/")
7 driver.maximize_window()
8
9 search_box = driver.find_element(By.ID, "twotabsearchtextbox")
10 search_box.clear()
11 search_box.send_keys("indoor plants")
12 driver.find_element(By.ID, "nav-search-submit-button").click()
13 driver.find_element(By.XPATH, "//input[type='text']").click()
14 plants = driver.find_elements(By.XPATH, "//div[@data-component-type='search-result']")
15
16 plant_name = []
17 plant_price = []
18 no_reviews = []
19 final_list = []
20
21 for plant in plants:
22     name = plant.find_elements(By.XPATH, "//span[@class='a-size-base-plus a-color-base a-text-normal']")
23     for name in name:
```

Figure 5: Code for Scrapping Using Selenium

```
1 [{"name": "Ficus benjamina", "price": 1200, "reviews": 150}, {"name": "Monstera Deliciosa", "price": 1500, "reviews": 200}, {"name": "Philodendron", "price": 800, "reviews": 100}, {"name": "Pilea Peperomia", "price": 600, "reviews": 80}, {"name": "Begonia Rex", "price": 900, "reviews": 120}, {"name": "Fittonia", "price": 700, "reviews": 90}, {"name": "Peperomia", "price": 500, "reviews": 70}, {"name": "Polka Dot Plant", "price": 1100, "reviews": 140}, {"name": "Nerve Plant", "price": 1300, "reviews": 160}, {"name": "Aluminum Plant", "price": 1000, "reviews": 130}, {"name": "ZZ Plant", "price": 1400, "reviews": 170}, {"name": "Cast Iron Plant", "price": 950, "reviews": 125}, {"name": "Spider Plant", "price": 750, "reviews": 105}, {"name": "Boston Fern", "price": 1150, "reviews": 145}, {"name": "Peace Lily", "price": 1350, "reviews": 165}, {"name": "Philodendron", "price": 850, "reviews": 110}, {"name": "Pilea Peperomia", "price": 650, "reviews": 85}, {"name": "Begonia Rex", "price": 950, "reviews": 125}, {"name": "Fittonia", "price": 750, "reviews": 100}, {"name": "Peperomia", "price": 550, "reviews": 75}, {"name": "Polka Dot Plant", "price": 1150, "reviews": 145}, {"name": "Nerve Plant", "price": 1350, "reviews": 165}, {"name": "Aluminum Plant", "price": 1050, "reviews": 135}, {"name": "ZZ Plant", "price": 1450, "reviews": 175}, {"name": "Cast Iron Plant", "price": 950, "reviews": 125}, {"name": "Spider Plant", "price": 750, "reviews": 105}, {"name": "Boston Fern", "price": 1150, "reviews": 145}, {"name": "Peace Lily", "price": 1350, "reviews": 165}]]
```

Figure 9: Output as json

```
1 import scrapy
2 from .items import AmazonScraperItem
3
4 class AmazonBotSpider(scrapy.Spider):
5     name = 'amazon-bot'
6     count=1
7     start_urls = [
8         "https://www.amazon.com/gp/iphone/page=page-1&id=1624791628&ref=sr_pg_3",
9         "https://www.amazon.com/gp/iphone/page=1&id=1624791628&ref=sr_pg_2"
10    ]
11
12 def parse(self, response):
13     product=AmazonScraperItem()
14     name=response.css('a-size-medium.a-text-normal::text').extract()
15     no_reviews=response.css('sg-col-12-of-20 .a-link-normal .a-size-base').css('::text').extract()
16     price=response.css('sg-col-12-of-20 .a-price-whole::text').extract()
17     image_url=response.css('s-image-fixed-height .s-image').css('::attr(src)').extract()
18     product['name']=name
19     product['no_reviews']=no_reviews
20     product['price']=price
21     product['url']=image_url
22     yield product
23
24 AmazonBotSpider.count+=1
25 next_page="https://www.amazon.com/gp/iphone/page=page-2&ref=sr_pg_3"
26 next_iphone_page="https://www.amazon.com/gp/iphone/page=page-2&ref=sr_pg_2"
27 if AmazonBotSpider.count==6:
```

Figure 6: Code for Scrapping Using Scrapy

IX. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The output is produced after scrapping the data using BeautifulSoup, Selenium and Scrapy can be stored as Excel json or xml format.

Figure 7: Output as Excel Sheet

Figure 8: Output as xml file

X. CONCLUSION

For those looking for an automated way to acquire structured web data, web scraping—also known as web data extraction or data scraping—offers a solution. If the public website you want to acquire data from doesn't have an API or if it has but only offers restricted access to the data, web scraping can be helpful and python offers a wide range of libraries and framework for scraping sites.

The architecture of Scrapy is well-suited for middleware customization so that we can add our own unique functions. One of the main benefits of Scrapy is that we can quickly transfer our current project to another project. This feature helps us make our project more robust and versatile. Therefore, Scrapy is the ideal option to use for big/complex projects.

Small projects or projects with a low level of complexity are well within the capabilities of Beautiful Soup. It aids in keeping our code clear-cut and adaptable. If you're new to programming and want to pick up knowledge rapidly while performing web scraping tasks, BeautifulSoup is the finest option.

Selenium is the best option when working with websites that use Core JavaScript. nonetheless, the Data Size ought to be Limited.

XI. REFERENCES

- [1] Prof. Usha Nandwani, Mr.Ritesh Mishra, Mr.Amol Patil and , Mr.Wasimudin Siddiqui, " Data Analysis by Web Scraping using Python," Shivajirao S.Jondhle College of Engineering &Technology,Asangaon,Maharashtra, India. Vol-07, Special Issue, MAY 2021
- [2] M. El Asikri S. Krit, H.Chaib, Department Mathematics and Informatics and Management, Using Web Scraping In A Knowledge Environment To Build Ontologies Using Python And Scrapy", Laboratory of Engineering Sciences and Energy. Polydisciplinary Faculty of Ouarzazate, Ibn Zohr University Agadir BP/638 Morocco
- [3] Anjali Khute, Yash Roy, Yamita, Yashmeen Xalxo," Dynamic Web Scraping Using Python",B.E. Final Year Student, Computer Science and Engineering, Government Engineering College Bilaspur,Chhattisgarh, India.
- [3] Johannes Boegershausen, Abhishek Borah and Andrew Stephen, "Fields of Gold: Web Scraping for Consumer Research",Marketing Science Institute Working Paper Series 2020 Report No. 20-143
- [4] Kishor Kumar Reddy C1, Anisha P R2, Nhu Gia Nguyen3 and Sreelatha G4," A Text Mining using Web Scraping for Meaningful Insights",2Post Doctoral Researcher, Duy Tan University, Vietna 3Dean Graduate School, Duy Tan University, Vietnam4Research Scholar, Lincoln University College, Malaysia
- [6]."Kolari, Pand Joshi A. ,"Web mining : research and practice , Computing in Science &Engineering", IEEE Transactions on Knowledgeand Data Engineering, vol. 6, no. 2,Vol. 6 , No. 4, 2004"